

Bureau of Crisis Prevention and Recovery

Prohibiting Cluster Munitions

Our chance to protect civilians

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) is the United Nations' global development network, advocating for change and connecting countries to knowledge, experience, and resources to help people build a better life. We are on the ground in 166 countries, working with them on their own solutions to global and national development challenges. As they develop local capacity, they draw on the people of UNDP and our wide range of partners.

The mission of the Bureau for Crisis Prevention and Recovery is to enhance UNDP's efforts for sustainable development, working with partners to reduce the incidence and impact of disasters and violent conflicts, and to establish the solid foundation for peace and recovery from crisis, thereby advancing the UN Millennium Development Goals on poverty reduction.

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PROHIBITING CLUSTER MUNITIONS: AN OPPORTUNITY AND A RESPONSIBILITY FOR HUMAN SECURITY

Cluster munitions are weapons that, when launched, scatter smaller bombs, called 'submunitions', over a wide area of land. They have been used in at least 30 countries and territories since World War II. They kill and injure civilians not only during attacks but also for years after the conflict has ended.

Because so many of the submunitions fail to explode as intended, these weapons continue to affect families and communities even after the fighting has ceased. They kill innocent civilians and their presence prevents safe farming, creates health and hygiene problems by blocking access to water and sanitation and hinders economic development.

Governments face a daunting challenge to rebuild fractured societies after periods of conflict. The process of rebuilding is only made harder in areas where cluster munitions have been used. Lives continue to be lost and land remains unused until clearance teams remove the explosive debris. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) partners with governments facing the challenge of making the environment safe for reconstruction and development.

In addition to this work, and in collaboration with other UN organizations and non-governmental organizations, UNDP helps draw attention to the unacceptable loss of life and severe hindrance to human development caused by cluster munitions. This effort has led, in part, to the launch of the Oslo Process in 2007—a global initiative to legally ban cluster munitions that cause unacceptable harm to civilians. Such a ban will not only protect future generations from the effects of cluster munitions but also require assistance for the victims of these weapons and increase efforts to remove the millions of explosive devices already present around the world.

2008 presents an opportunity for the international community to come together and prohibit these weapons that harm thousands of innocent children, women and civilians. For governments committed to the protection of the vulnerable, this is not just an opportunity, it is a responsibility.

WHAT ARE CLUSTER MUNITIONS?

Cluster munitions are weapons that consist of a container that disperses multiple smaller bombs called submunitions. These submunitions scatter over a wide area, often killing or injuring civilians if they are used in or near populated places. Although designed to explode when they strike the ground, many of the bomblets fail to function and remain as deadly explosive remnants. Like landmines, these lethal devices can continue to kill and injure for decades.

KEY FACTS

- Cluster bombs have killed and injured civilians in conflict since World War II. Unexploded submunitions remaining from attacks undertaken in the 1970s continue to claim lives today.
- To date, they have been used in at least 30 countries and territories: Afghanistan, Albania, Angola, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cambodia, Chad, Chechnya, Croatia, Democratic Republic of Congo, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Falklands/Malvinas, Iraq, Israel, Kosovo, Kuwait, Lao PDR, Lebanon, Montenegro, Nagorno-Karabakh, Saudi Arabia, Serbia, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Syria, Tajikistan, Uganda, Viet Nam and Western Sahara.¹

- Billions of submunitions are now stockpiled, ready to be used by some 75 countries.²
- Worldwide estimates of the number of civilians killed or maimed by cluster bombs so far run into the tens of thousands.³
- One-third of reported cluster bomb casualties are children.⁴
- On 23 February 2007, 46 states agreed in Oslo, Norway to conclude in 2008 a treaty prohibiting cluster munitions that cause unacceptable harm to civilians; 68 states participated in a treaty preparation meeting in Lima, Peru in May 2007; 138 states participated in another treaty preparation meeting in Vienna, Austria in December 2007; and 103 participated in Wellington, New Zealand in February 2008.

RESPONDING TO CLUSTER MUNITION CONTAMINATION:

Various activities are underway at country level to address the threat of cluster munitions. With techniques similar to those used for landmine clearance, teams can slowly make land safe for the local population. Other teams work with people living in affected areas to identify ways in which communities can live more safely until clearance is undertaken. Still other teams help families and survivors of cluster munition incidents by providing immediate and long-term health care and rehabilitation, and helping them reintegrate, both economically and socially, into their communities. UNDP provides direct support to governments and organizations that undertake this vital work.

CASE STUDY

LEBANON

In many parts of southern Lebanon tobacco is a mainstay of agricultural production. This crop is the only one that is subsidized by the government, and each farmer has a quota that can be produced and sold to the state tobacco authority each year at a set price. In a precarious environment, this offers agricultural producers some degree of stability.

Abbas Khreiban farms this land with six families, supporting approximately 50 people. The seven families have two separate areas where they grow tobacco, each consisting of approximately three hectares of land. Following the 2006 conflict, all the harvest was lost as Abbas and the other families were unsure whether their land was free from cluster munitions.

In 2007 and 2008, only one parcel of land was used as the other was littered with cluster munitions. This translates into a loss of an estimated 6,000 kilograms of tobacco every year or \$3,500 per family.

Unexploded cluster munitions also contaminated the area surrounding their greenhouse, where the tobacco plants are grown before being transplanted in the larger fields. Abbas estimates he removed more than 200 M77 sub-munitions. He stopped doing so when he found one of his children handling a cluster munition in an effort to remove it. Since then, the Mine Action Group has removed all the remaining unexploded munitions from around the greenhouse.

It is unclear when the remaining fields will be cleared but Abbas and the six families he works with hope that by next season, some three years after the war, they will once again be producing crops on all of their land.

CLUSTER MUNITIONS IMPEDE DEVELOPMENT IN COUNTRIES RECOVERING FROM CONFLICT. DEATHS AND INJURIES AFFECT FAMILIES AND COMMUNITIES PSYCHOLOGICALLY, SOCIALLY AND ECONOMICALLY. PEOPLE ARE FACED WITH POSSIBLE INJURY OR DEATH OR THE LOSS OF FOOD AND LIVELIHOODS. FOR GOVERNMENTS WEAKENED BY YEARS OF CONFLICT, THESE PROBLEMS, COUPLED WITH THE COST OF REBUILDING VITAL INFRASTRUCTURE, MAKES ACHIEVING THE MILLENNIUM DEVELOPMENT GOALS A CHALLENGE.

CAUSING HARM

➔ the physical, psychological and financial cost

For survivors of cluster munition incidents, the physical and psychological distress is often devastating. The immediate cost of hospital treatment, if it is accessible or available, can be higher than many individuals can afford. Long-term care, rehabilitation and reintegration may not be affordable or even exist in the region. For adults, the ability to engage in livelihood activities is often severely compromised. For children, education may come to a halt, reducing their chances of finding work in the future.

When a victim is killed, the impact on the family is devastating. In many countries, the most common victims of cluster munitions are adult men, who often represent the main source of household income. Loss of this income only adds to the personal tragedy of losing a father, brother or husband.

DESTROYING LIVELIHOODS

➔ removing access and reducing opportunity

Cluster munition contamination has affected the livelihoods of people in numerous countries. A common problem presented by unexploded cluster munitions is that access to land becomes more difficult or more dangerous.

After the bombing of Kosovo in 1999, more than 1,700 hectares of agricultural land had to be cleared of cluster munitions before it could be safely farmed. In Lebanon, cluster munitions contamination led to the loss of cash

crops such as olives, citrus fruits and tobacco as farmers were unable to irrigate or harvest crops, and seasonal migrant labourers were unable to secure employment.⁵ Grazing land is also affected by cluster munition contamination. The most likely time for Afghani children to be involved in a cluster munition incident is while tending animals.⁶

In an environment contaminated by cluster munitions, everyday livelihood and income-generating activities can be a potential threat—denying people their fundamental human right to security. People are forced to balance their need for land with the threat of being killed or injured.

INCREASING COSTS

➔ making development more difficult

Cluster munitions not only affect livelihoods, but also impact the vital infrastructure necessary for development.

In Lao PDR, internationally funded infrastructure development projects have spent at least \$20 million on the clearance of unexploded ordnance—approximately 50 percent of which are unexploded cluster munitions. These projects include the construction of roads, clinics, schools, water pipelines, irrigation structures, power lines and dams and assistance to rural small holders.⁷

In one project designed to provide power to more than 33,000 rural households in northern Lao, clearance of unexploded ordnance amounted to more than 5 percent of the total project costs. In one road reconstruction project, ordnance contamination was responsible for an additional \$1.2 million in costs and was cited as a key reason for a delay in the implementation of the project.

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DRAINING RESOURCES

➔ dealing with cluster munitions

For humanitarian donors and affected governments, cluster munition contamination is costly. An estimated \$30 million was spent in the immediate aftermath of the conflict in Kosovo.⁸ In Lebanon, the clearance of cluster munitions dropped during the five-week crisis period in 2006 will require a two-year combined effort of five international clearance organizations and a UN coordinating body.

Cluster munitions and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs)

The presence of cluster munition impedes the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). For example:

GOAL 1: END HUNGER & EXTREME POVERTY

Trying to reduce poverty and hunger is made more difficult in areas where cluster munitions are restricting access to vital agricultural land.

GOAL 2: UNIVERSAL EDUCATION

Cluster munitions can restrict access to schools or slow down their reconstruction thus jeopardizing children from achieving primary education.

GOAL 3: GENDER EQUITY

Women are likely to suffer greater inequities as a result of cluster munitions. Female victims are less likely to receive medical care and prostheses and are more likely to face stigma and abandonment when injured or disabled. In addition, when women are widowed as a result of cluster munitions, they often face unemployment.⁹

GOAL 4: CHILD HEALTH

The presence of cluster munitions slows down efforts to reduce child mortality. Cluster munitions not only kill and maim children, their presence in communities jeopardizes a child's right to health and play in a safe environment.

UNDP IN ACTION

“The characteristics of these munitions, with their inherent inaccuracy and frequent malfunctioning, make them particularly indiscriminate both at the time of use and long after conflicts have ended.”¹⁰

UNITED NATIONS SECRETARY-GENERAL BAN KI-MOON

The use of cluster munitions poses significant challenges for international humanitarian law. With a presence in all countries currently known to be contaminated by cluster munitions, UNDP sees first hand both the immediate humanitarian impact and the longer-term socio-economic and development impact of cluster munitions on people and communities.

As part of its larger mine action work, UNDP is working together with governments, other UN organizations and non-governmental organizations to clear explosive remnants of war including landmines and cluster munitions in 17 of the countries currently known to be affected by cluster munitions.

Witnessing the consistent harm caused by cluster munitions coupled with the challenges that these weapons pose for post-conflict governments and humanitarian and development assistance, UNDP has since 2003 been committed to strengthening international law so as to put an end to the proliferation of these weapons. In partnership with other UN organizations, UNDP has supported research, undertaken technical analysis, and worked to raise awareness of the humanitarian and development challenges that these weapons cause through media campaigns and participation in expert meetings.

UNDP has worked with other UN colleagues to develop a strong common position on cluster munitions. The United Nations Secretary-General has urged member states to address the horrendous humanitarian, human rights and developmental effects of cluster munitions by concluding a legally binding instrument of international humanitarian law.

In collaboration with its 166 country offices, UNDP is administering sponsorship programmes to allow developing and low-income countries to play a prominent role in conferences aimed at negotiating a treaty to prohibit cluster munitions that cause unacceptable harm to civilians. UNDP has also assisted governments in organizing regional meetings such as those held in Costa Rica in August 2007, Serbia in October 2007 and Zambia in March 2008.

UNDP POLICY

On 17 September 2007, the United Nations adopted the following position:

The UN calls on Member States to address immediately the horrendous humanitarian, human rights and development effects of cluster munitions by concluding a legally binding instrument of international humanitarian law that:

- **prohibits the use, development, production, stockpiling and transfer of cluster munitions that cause unacceptable harm to civilians;**
- **requires the destruction of current stockpiles of those munitions; and**
- **provides for clearance, risk education and other risk mitigation activities, victim assistance, assistance and cooperation, and compliance and transparency measures.**

Until such a treaty is adopted, the UN calls on States to take domestic measures to immediately freeze the use and transfer of all cluster munitions.¹¹

UNDP supports the UN position and the Secretary-General’s call for immediate action to prohibit cluster munitions that cause unacceptable harm to civilians. UNDP will support all efforts toward an international legally binding instrument that will prohibit the use, production and transfer of such cluster munitions as soon as possible. UNDP therefore supports wholeheartedly the Oslo Process, which has set forth to finalize an international treaty in 2008.

As has been stated in February 2008 at the Wellington Conference on Cluster Munitions “From what UN agencies with a presence on the ground have seen, all cluster munitions that have been used and... are still stockpiled, cause unacceptable harm to civilians. They should be prohibited. Those states that argue for the retention of other cluster munitions should provide data on their impact and possible harm to civilians based on tests that accurately reflect real conflict situations.”¹²

MESSAGE FROM DIDIER DROGBA

I believe in giving people a chance. I know from the experience of my own country, Cote d'Ivoire, how terrible war can be for individuals, families and communities. But I also know that if people are given a chance they can achieve many things, even after a devastating conflict. Cluster bombs take that chance away. For people who are injured or killed by unexploded cluster bombs, or who live in poverty because they cannot farm their land, it is as though the war never ended.

Although many brave technicians are working every day to remove and destroy cluster bombs left over from wars in places like Afghanistan, Vietnam and Lebanon, surely the only way to really give people hope and the chance they deserve is to remove cluster bombs altogether—by banning them. I hope that the international community, with the support of the United Nations, can take this opportunity to make this dreadful weapon illegal, and in doing so give people and communities around the world the chance to live in peace and prosperity.

Je pense qu'on doit donner une chance aux gens. J'ai l'expérience de la guerre, dans mon propre pays la Côte d'Ivoire, et je sais à quel point elle peut être terrible pour les personnes, les familles et les communautés. Mais je sais aussi que si les personnes ont une opportunité, elles peuvent réaliser beaucoup de choses, même dans un pays dévasté par la guerre ! Les Bombes à Sous-Munitions (BASM) leur enlèvent cette chance. Lorsque vous êtes blessé ou tué par une BASM qui n'a pas explosé, ou lorsque vous vivez dans la pauvreté parce que vous ne pouvez pas exploiter vos champs, c'est comme si la guerre n'était pas terminée.

Même si nombre de techniciens courageux travaillent chaque jour pour enlever et détruire les bombes qui subsistent encore après la guerre dans des pays comme l'Afghanistan, le Vietnam et le Liban, la seule façon de réellement donner une chance aux gens est de les bannir, pour qu'elles n'existent plus jamais ! J'espère qu'avec le soutien des Nations Unies, la communauté internationale parviendra à interdire cette arme terrible, et ce faisant, à donner leur chance aux populations et communautés du monde entier de vivre en paix et en prospérité.

Soccer star Didier Drogba is a UNDP Goodwill Ambassador for the fight against poverty. Drogba is native of Cote d'Ivoire and currently plays for Chelsea F.C. in the English Premier League.

1. Handicap International, 'Circle of Impact: The Fatal Footprint of Cluster Munitions on People and Communities', Brussels, Belgium, 2007; and Human Rights Watch fact sheet on cluster munitions.
2. International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), 'Survey of Cluster Munitions Produced and Stockpiled', published in 'Report on the Expert Meeting: Humanitarian, Military, Technical and Legal Challenges of Cluster Munitions, Montreux, Switzerland, 18–20 April 2007', Geneva, Switzerland, 2007, pp 23–25.
3. Handicap International, 'Circle of Impact: The Fatal Footprint of Cluster Munitions on People and Communities', Brussels, Belgium, 2007.
4. Ibid.
5. UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 'A Lasting Legacy: The Deadly Impact of Cluster Bombs in Southern Lebanon', 2006.
6. Figures taken from the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) Afghanistan Mine/Explosive Remnants of War (ERW) Database, 1978–2006.
7. Analysis of Asia Development Bank and World Bank funded infrastructure projects in Lao PDR by Landmine Action for UNDP. Data taken from a total of 15 projects that were infrastructure projects for which information was fully available. The total number of relevant projects will be greater and research is ongoing to assess this.
8. Landmine Action, 'Cluster Munitions in Kosovo: Analysis of Use, Contamination and Casualties', London, England, 2007, p 52.
9. Women's International League for Peace and Freedom, 'Women and Cluster Munitions', available online at www.wilpf.int.ch/disarmament/clustermunitions.
10. Message from the Secretary General Ban Ki-moon to the 2007 Meeting of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons, Geneva, 7 November 2007.
11. UN Position on Cluster Munitions. This position was formally adopted at the UN Principals Meeting of the Inter-Agency Coordination Group on Mine Action held at UN Headquarters in New York City on 17 September 2007.
12. Wellington Conference on Cluster Munitions, Opening address on behalf of the UN Mine Action Team delivered by Ms. Hilde Frafjord Johnson, Deputy Executive Director, UNICEF, 18–22 February 2008.

Research done in collaboration with Landmine Action, United Kingdom.